

One Step Treatment of Polyester Fabrics by Alkali and TiO₂ NPs and its Effect on their Functional Performance and Dye-ability

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Abstract:

This article is aiming to study the effect of simultaneous treatment of PET and PET/C blended fabrics with sodium hydroxide and TiO₂ nanoparticles (NPs) on their functional performance and dye-ability. The advance of the suggested method is production polyester fabrics imparted new and better functional performance (antimicrobial activity and ultraviolet protection) properties durable in their repeated laundering processes. The modified and dyed fabrics will be investigated by using: SEM, EDX, FTIR. The color strength (K/S) and the fastness properties of dyed PET and PET/C blended fabrics samples were assessed. The obtained results showed that, dyeing polyester fabrics after treatment with alkali and NPs simultaneously have a tangible effect on both % reduction of colony forming unit (% CFU) and ultraviolet protection factor (UPF) properties. The dyed samples appeared enhancement in the color strength and fastness properties. The suggested approach is facile and benign to apply on industrial scale without cost investment.

Keywords: Alkali Hydrolysis, Antimicrobial, Dyeing. PET and PET/C Fabrics, TiO₂ NPs, UV Protection

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1. Introduction

Textiles may be treated with antimicrobial agents for a range of reasons depending on the market sector and application area. Antimicrobials are typically applied to give textiles improved resilience against microorganisms (e. g. preventing destruction of polymers, discoloration) and increased durability of the textile leading to longer lifetime of use [1-2]. Antimicrobials can also be used to protect textiles against colonization of odor-forming bacteria [3-4]. They may also be applied to textiles to play a role in addressing hygiene in clinical and sensitive environments by minimizing the chances for microbial colonization of textiles and the potential for transfer from fabric surfaces [5-6].

However antimicrobial treatments can provide consumers with an option to consciously reduce the frequency and/or intensity of laundering which can give potential for significant savings in water use, energy consumption and reduced need for chemical consumables in textile care. Considering that the majority of resources used in the life of a textile occurs in the use and care phase this can be a significant environmental benefit. For consumers looking for ways to reduce environmental footprint in daily life, textiles that require less intensity of care can provide a way to contribute to this goal [6].

Nano-metal oxides have created a new approach for remarkable applications as an attractive multi-functional finishing material. TiO₂ NPs have unique properties such as higher stability, long lasting, safe and broad-spectrum antibiosis. This makes TiO₂ NPs applicable in many fields such as: self-cleaning [7], antimicrobial [8], UV protecting [8], purification the environment [9], gas sensors [10], high efficient solar cell [11], and Dye degradation in textile effluent due to their photo-activity property [12].

Industrial wet processing line for natural and man-made fabrics includes desizing and scouring steps in alkaline medium [13], which may lead to the creation of additional functional groups (COOH and OH) in PET macromolecules, it seems of a great interest to clarify the possibility of adding TiO₂ NPs in alkaline treatment bath as a practical alternative to traditional approach [14].

It is known that, the wet processing line in dyeing and finishing factories consists of these main stages (Desizing - Scouring - Bleaching - Dyeing - Finishing). Sizing and scouring are used for removing the starch in case of PET/C blended fabrics or polyvinyl alcohol in case of PET fabric. These stages are processed in an aqueous alkaline medium. The idea of the research lies in the possibility of adding nano-metal oxides in the alkaline medium so that the removal of the sizing agents takes place and at the same time, the finishing process is carrying out. This reduces the cost and may pave the way for the direct use of nano-metal oxides easily and conveniently on the production line without any technological investment. Therefore, this article is concerning with studying the effect of simultaneous treatment of polyester fabrics with sodium hydroxide and TiO₂ NPs simultaneously on their functional performance and dye-ability. This technique is paving the way for NPs to be widely implemented on a wet processing line in industry and became more economic for the textile finisher.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

- Desized and Bleached polyester (PET) 100% Trevira (165 gr/m²) and polyester / cotton (PET/C) blended 50/50 (236 gr/m²) woven fabrics were used throughout this work provided by local textile industries. The fabrics before use was washed in a aqueous solution containing 2.0 g/L nonionic detergent for 30 min at 60°C with liquor to goods ratio (M : L) of 1: 40, then rinsed with distilled water and dried at ambient temperature.
- All chemical used in this work [Titanium dioxide nanoparticles (TiO₂NPs) emulsion (aqueous, 30%) – Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), hydrochloric acid (were purchased from Fluka and have been used as received.
- *Bacillus mycoides* (*B. m*) (Gram positive bacterium), *Escherichia coli* (*E. c*) (Gram negative bacterium), and *Candida albicans* (*C. a*) (nonfilamentous fungus) were used for estimation of antimicrobial potency of control and treated samples. Microorganisms were obtained from the culture collection of the Microbial Chemistry Department, Division of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, National Research Centre of Egypt.

Disperse dye (Dianix Yellow E3GE), direct dye (Sirius S-2G) and soaping agent (Sera Fast), were kindly supplied by Dye Star Company. Acetic acid, Dispersing agent, Sodium acetate, Sodium carbonate, non-anionic agent, Sodium sulphate and sodium sulfite were purchased from Fluka and have been used as received.

Chemical Structure of C.I. Direct Dye Yellow

Chemical Structure of C.I. Disperse Dye Yellow

2.2 Methods

2.2.1. Alkaline Treatment of Polyester Fabrics

The alkaline treatment of PET and PET/C blended fabrics was carried out according to the method described in [13], using a high temperature, high pressure laboratory dyeing machine. Required volume from the prepared and calibrated of alkali aqueous solution was placed in stainless-steel bowl. The fabrics samples were immersed in the solutions and the sealed bowls were rotated in a closed bath containing ethylene glycol at selected temperature. The liquor- to- fabrics ratio (M: L) was 1:50. The bath temperature increased at rate of 2°C/min. After the predetermined durations, the samples were removed from the bath, rinsed repeatedly with distilled water, neutralized with a solution of 1% hydrochloric acid and rinsed. The samples were then dried at 100°C, cooled in a dessicator, and weighed [14].

2.2.2. Polyester Fabrics Loaded by TiO₂ NPs

The simultaneous treatment of polyester fabrics with NaOH and TiO₂ NPs was carried out as follows: The required volume from the prepared and calibrated of alkali aqueous solution was placed in stainless-steel bowl in presence TiO₂ NPs by using 1.0 g/l (Scheme 1). The fabrics samples were immersed in the solutions and the sealed bowls were rotated in a closed bath containing ethylene glycol at selected temperature. The liquor- to- fabrics ratio (M: L) was 1:50. The bath temperature increased at rate of 2°C/min. After the predetermined durations, the samples were removed from the bath, rinsed repeatedly with distilled water, neutralized with a solution of 1% hydrochloric acid and rinsed. The samples were then dried at 100°C, cooled in a dessicator, and weighed.

Scheme (1): The simultaneous treatment of polyester fabric with NaOH and TiO₂ NPs

2.2.3. Durability Testing Method

In order to evaluate the Ti₂O NPs adhesion to the polyester fabrics, the treated fabric was washed five times according to a standard method AATCC Test Method (61-1989). One such test takes about 45 min under the action of detergent solution. Every one washing cycle represents that of five typical home launderings. In our approach, washing of textiles was performed at washing temperature settings of 71°C. After this process, the textiles were dried at 105°C.

2.2.4. Dyeing Procedure

2.2.4.1. Dyeing of PET Fabrics

The dyeing bath with disperse dye (1.0%) set as shown in scheme (1). The pH was adjusted at 5-5.5, dyeing was performed at 30°C for 10 minutes and the temperature was gradually raised by 1:2 °C/min, 130°C, then dyeing was continued for 60 min at 130°C, and then thoroughly rinsed and washed in a wash bath containing 1.0g/l sodium sulfite (reduction clearing) for 20 min at 70°C and finally rinsed with hot and cold water then dried in air.

(1%Dye+ water+ Acetic Acid+ 1%Dispersing Agent+ 2g/l Sodium Sulphate)

Scheme (2): Dyeing Method of PET Fabric

2.2.4.2. Dyeing of PET/C blended fabrics (One Step)

The dyeing bath with disperse and direct dyes was set as shown in scheme (2). The pH was adjusted at 9.0, dyeing was performed at 30°C for 10 minutes and the temperature was gradually raised by 1:2 °C/min, 130°C, then dyeing was continued for 30 minutes at 130°C, and Reduce temperature to 80°C contain the dyed samples for 20 minutes, and then thoroughly rinsed and washed in a wash bath containing 2.0g/l detergent (Soaping) for 10 min at 60°C and finally rinsed with hot and cold water then dried in air.

(0.5% Direct Dye+ 0.5% Disperse Dye +Water+ Acetic Acid+1% Dispersing Agent+ 2%Sodium Acetate+2% Sodium Sulphate)

Scheme (3): One step Dyeing Method of PET/C Blend Fabrics 2.3

Analysis

2.3.1. Carboxylic content

Carboxylic content was determined according to the method described in [15].

2.3.2. Antimicrobial Activity

Antimicrobial activity of PET fabrics loaded with TiO₂NPs was quantified using the following method: Shake Flask method expressed throughout (%) reduction of bacterial count by calculated colony forming unit (CFU). In this method the antimicrobial activity of immobilized antimicrobial samples is determined under dynamic contact conditions according to ASTM standard test method 2149 (2001) [16].

2.3.3. Surface Morphology

The structures and surface morphology of the alkali treated polyester fabrics and loaded with TiO₂ NPs were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM T20). Electron dispersive Emission X-ray. EDX mode was applied for the elemental composition analysis. Gold layer was coated on the fabrics surfaces before the examination.

2.3.4. The surface Chemistry

The surface chemistry of the PET and PET/C blended fabrics, partially hydrolyzed and loaded by TiO₂NPs were investigated using the Fourier Transformation Infrared (FT-IR) spectrometer, model NFXUS 670, NICLET USA. The measurements were carried in the spectral range from 4000 to 500 cm⁻¹. Reflection percentage measurement technique (R %) was applied to all investigated samples.

2.3.5. Ultraviolet Protection Factor (UPF)

UPF was determined using UV-Shimadzu 3101 PC Spectrophotometer. It is a double beam direct ratio measuring system. It consists of photometer unit and a PC computer. The UPF values were automatically calculated on the basis of the recorded data in accordance with Australia/ New Zealand standard AS/NZS 4395:1995 [17].

Table 1 - UV protection and classification according to AS/NZS 4395:1995

UVP	UPF classification
Excellent	40, 45, 50, 50+
Very good	25, 30, 35
Good	15, 20
Non- ratable	5, 10

2.3.6. The Color Strength

The effect of loading by TiO₂ NPs on the dye-ability of PET and PET/C blended fabrics partially hydrolyzed were investigated. The color strength (K/S) of dyed polyester fabrics were evaluated by Ultra scan spectrophotometer, Hunter Lap, by light reflectance technique. The K/S values of the dyed samples were automatically calculated according to Kubelka-Munk equation (1) [18].

$$\text{Color strength } K/S = (1 - R)^2 / (2R) \quad (1)$$

Where, K, S, and R are the absorption coefficient, scattering coefficient, and reflectance, respectively.

2.3.6.1. Color Fastness

2.3.6.2. Color Fastness to Washing

It was determined according to the AATCC test method 61-1996 (150). The specimens were sewed between two pieces, one piece made of the same kind of fiber as that of the textile to be tested, the second piece made of cotton or wool in the case of polyester. The composite specimen was immersed into an aqueous solution containing 5.0 g/l soap and 2.0g/l sodium carbonate at 60°C for 15 minutes. The samples then were rinsed with warm water, and neutralizing with acetic acid. Evaluation of the wash was established using the gray scale reference for color change [19].

2.3.6.3. Color Fastness to Crocking

The color fastness to crocking was determined according to the AATCC test 8-1996 [19]. This designated for determining the degree of color which may be transferred from the surface of the colored fabric to other surface by rubbing. Dry and wet crocking tests were applied.

2.3.6.4. Color Fastness to Perspiration

Two artificial perspiration solutions were made as follow, acidic solution and alkaline solution, this test was carried according to the AATCC test method 15-1997 [19].

2.3.6.5. Color Fastness to Light

This test was evaluated according to the BS (test no: 1006-1978) in order to determine the degree of color resistance to photo degradation.

3. Results and Discussion

Alkali treatment of polyester fabrics has been used to enhancement the dye-ability, wet-ability, and modification the surface properties of PET fabrics. This treatment leads to a partial hydrolysis of surface fabric and produces new properties on PET [19].

Effect of Alkali on Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) [20]

To study the effect of suggested method applied here for the ability of activated surface on binding efficiency of NPs (Simultaneous treatment of polyester fabrics in the presence of sodium hydroxide and TiO₂ NPs). PET fabrics were initially treated by alkali solutions, before loading with TiO₂ NPs. It well known that, alkali treatment causes a significant increase of OH and COOH groups on the surface of polyester fibers. These data were experimentally proved by the estimation of functional groups creating on the surfaces of polyester fabrics before and after the alkali treatment through carboxylic content measurement.

It was found (Table 1) that the surface of alkali treated fabrics in general, PET have an increase in its carboxylic content rather than parent. Alkali treatment causes outstanding increase in carboxylic content from 3.5 to 13.1 meq/100gr fabric and 6.2 to 22.4, irrespectively. Therefore, the interaction between the activated textile surface by alkali and TiO₂ NPs is electrostatic in its nature, since the textile surface is negatively charged as a result of the activation and formation of COOH and OH groups on the surface. This may be enhancement the loading and binding of TiO₂ NPs onto the fabrics surfaces, similar observations after partial hydrolysis of polyester fabrics were reported [13-14; 21].

Alkaline treatment (at constant concentration from TiO₂NPs 0.2 g/l) of both PET and PET/C blended fabrics leads to a loss in weight of the fabrics (Table 2). Hydrolysis was found to proceed, but with a low weight loss (PET = 1.5%, PET/C = 1.9 at 60 min. and 90°C) when fabrics were treated with aqueous NaOH solution having low concentration (0.5N). The weight loss increased with increasing NaOH concentration, irrespectively of the type of treated fabrics. However, a high level of weight reduction occurs in the case of PET fabric.

However, a high level of weight reduction occurs in the case of PET, than in the case PET/C blended fabrics, especially at high concentration of NaOH solution (2.0 mol/l). For instance, a weight loss of 7.9 % was obtained in the case of PET fabric at sodium hydroxide concentration equal to 2.0 mol/l. This contrasts with a weight loss of 7.1 % after alkaline treatment of PET/C blended fabric under the same conditions.

Table (1): Carboxylic Content of Bleached (H) and Hydrolyzed (H) Polyester Fabrics

Fabrics	Carboxylic Content (meq/100 gr. Fabric)
PET→B	3.50
PET→B→H (Weight loss % = 6.6)	13.1
PET/C→B	6.20
PET/C→B→H (Weight loss % = 5.5)	22.4

Table (2): Effect of NaOH Concentration on the Weight Loss % of Alkali Treated Polyester Fabrics

Treatment Time (min.)	Dependence of Weight Loss % for polyester Fabrics on Sodium Hydroxide Concentration (mol/L) at:							
	0.5		1.0		1.5		2.0	
	PET	PET/C	PET	PET/C	PET	PET/C	PET	PET/C
10	1.9	1.5	2.7	2.1	3.0	2.7	5.0	3.1
20	3.5	2.5	4.4	2.8	5.2	3.1	5.5	3.5
30	4.3	3.1	4.8	3.7	5.4	3.6	6.1	4.0
45	5.1	4.1	5.6	4.5	6.2	4.5	6.6	5.0
60	5.4	4.3	5.9	4.9	6.6	5.5	7.9	7.1

Treatment Conditions: [TiO₂ NPs], 0.2 g/l; Temperature, 90°C; M : L, 1 : 50.

3.1. Characterization of polyester Fabrics Loaded with TiO₂ NPs

3.1.1. Scan Electron Microscope (SEM)

SEM was used to investigate the presence of TiO₂ NPs and/or incorporate NPs on the surfaces of fabric (Fig. 1). It was shown that the surface structure of parent fabrics was retained stable. At higher magnification, the surfaces of the fabric is more distinguished. The parent fabrics (Fig. A and D) has smooth, round, clean and without any pits can be seen on its surface.

The effect of alkali treatment on the surface of fabric was clarified in the micrographs (B) and (E), where the surfaces of partially hydrolyzed fabrics became pitted with holes distributed randomly on the fabric surfaces. The surface of alkali treated fibers were rough that can be due to etching of the NaOH to the fabric surfaces which resulting from hydrolysis of the short chains and amorphous regain in the polymer matrix. A few numbers of pits on the fiber surface can be observed on the fabrics by adding TiO₂ NPs to the reaction medium. Also, some fibers started to link to each other and a thin film were covering the structure of fabrics surfaces. Fig. C and F reveals the unevenly distributed aggregates of TiO₂ NPs with dimensions on the surface of the modified PET fabric.

Figures C and F show TiO₂ NPs coated the surface of partially hydrolyzed polyester fabrics, at higher magnification we showed a random distribution of TiO₂ NPs on the surface of alkali treated fabrics compared to the hydrolyzed fabrics in absence NPs, which had some cracks and voids produced on its surface under the effect of alkaline hydrolysis, these cracks contained more TiO₂ NPs entrapped inside them. The particles have large size could be easily removed from the fiber surface, whereas the small one could penetrate the polymer matrix and adhere more strongly to the fabric. EDX micrographs (C and F) that confirmed the deposited materials on the polyester fabrics surfaces was TiO₂ NPs.

A

B

Figure (1): SEM and EDX Micrographs of Bleached, Partially Hydrolyzed and Dyed PET Fabrics Loaded with TiO₂ NPs* (X2000)

[A] PET→B→H→D (Blank) [B] PET→B→H+TiO₂ [C] PET→B→(H+TiO₂)→D
 [D] PET/C→B→H→D (Blank) [E] PET/C→B→H+TiO₂ [F] PET/C→B→H+TiO₂→D
 *After One Washing Cycle; AATCC Test Method (61-1989).

3.1.2. EDX

EDX spectra of the polyester fabrics coated with TiO₂ NPs after one washing cycle are shown in fig. (1). On the basis of these spectra, we can conclude that, the atomic structure of coated material consisted of Ti and O₂. This finding is proved even after one washing cycle (5 home washings), TiO₂ is still bind to the polyester fabrics surface (Table 3). EDX investigation also appeared higher atomic weight % of Ti on partially hydrolyzed PET and PET/C blended fabrics and loaded Ti NPs, (Ti atomic weight % was 2.39 and 3.31 respectively). This is more conformation that TiO₂ NPs have good adhesion to the alkali treated polyester fabrics.

Table (3): Ti Content of Polyester Fabrics and Loaded with NPs

No.	Fabrics	Atomic % on Polyester surface of Ti:
1	PET→B (Blank)	0.00
2	PET→B→H	0.00
3	PET→B→H+ TiO ₂ 1 g/l	2.39
4	PET→B (Blank)	0.00
5	PET/C→B→H	0.00
6	PET/C→B→H+ TiO ₂ 1 g/l	3.31

*After One Washing Cycle; AATCC Test Method (61-1989).

3.1.3. FTIR

Table (4) shows the characteristic peaks attributed to >C=O and —OH groups of parent, alkali treated and dyed fabrics. the intensity of characteristic peaks ascribed to OH at 3300 and 3332.4 cm⁻¹ and the peak attributed to C=O (carboxylic acid) at 1714.7 and 1715.6 cm⁻¹ was detected, but no change was observed at other peaks. The intensities of the peaks ascribed to OH and COOH increased for polyester treated with NPs compared with parent fabrics. Also, comparing partially hydrolyzed polyester, and alkali treated in presence TiO₂ NPs and dyed with parent fabrics indicated a decrease in the intensities of the peaks ascribed to C=O (carboxylic acid) at 1714.7 and 1715.6 cm⁻¹ to 1712.2 and 1711.4 cm⁻¹ respectively. This is prove the possibility of reaction between TiO₂NPs and polymer chains [21]. The FTIR charts of alkali treated PET fabrics showed appearing new peaks at the

position 764.9 and 702.2 cm^{-1} with PET, which proves the ionic interaction between carboxylate groups existed on the fabric surfaces and Ti present in the reaction medium, similar finding was reported [22].

Table (4): FT-IR Absorption Bands of Bleached, Partially Hydrolyzed and Dyed (D) Polyester Fabrics and Loaded with TiO_2 NPs*

No.	Fabrics	Absorption Bands of Functional Groups (>C=O — OH) Affected After Treatment with TiO_2 NPs				New Absorption Bands Appeared	
		>C=O		—OH		Position (Cm^{-1})	Intensity
		Position(Cm^{-1})	Intensity	Position (Cm^{-1})	Intensity		
1	PET→B→H→D (Blank)	1714.7	91.4	3321.7	98.7	-	-
2	PET→B→H→ TiO_2 →D	1712.2	95.3	3300.2	94.2	764.9	99.1
3	PET/C→B→H→D (Blank)	1715.6	93.3	3327.4	99.1	-	-
4	PET/C→B→H→ TiO_2 →D	1711.4	98.4	3323.4	93.2	702.2	93.0

*After One Washing Cycle; AATCC Test Method (61-1989).

3.2. The Functional Performance of PET fabric

3.2.1. Antimicrobial Properties

Fig. 2 and 3 indicated that, all fabrics showed, after one washing cycle, a high antimicrobial activity. In fact, the % CFU for all tested polyester fabrics samples are significant, whereas it is null for all the blank samples. The role of activation of polyester fabrics with alkali hydrolysis in presence TiO_2 NPs on the antimicrobial activity seems to be more significant as the samples were laundered repeatedly in launder-Ometer.

It was found that, the bioactivity of the substrates activated by alkali hydrolysis in presence NPs became significantly different (Fig. 2 and 3). The decrease in antimicrobial activity of PET and PET/C fabrics activated occurred progressively as the number of washes increased. Under these activation conditions both PET and PET/C fabrics has lost about 9.0 % and 11.0 %, respectively, its antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *B. mycoides* after 5 Launder- Ometer washes.

In contrast, in case of dyed PET and PET/C blended fabrics after loading with TiO_2 NPs, the antimicrobial functions were slightly reduced to certain level. After 5 washing cycles the dyed PET and PET/C fabrics could still provide 70.0 % and 80.0 % microbial reduction against *B. mycoides*. This proves that, the feasibility of applying simultaneous treatment of polyester fabrics with sodium hydroxide and TiO_2 NPs as finishing method to prepare polyester fabrics imparted antimicrobial property.

Figure (2): Antimicrobial Activity of PET Fabric and Loaded with TiO_2 NPs, Determined by Shake Flask Method. (WC = Washing Cycle by AATCC Test Method (61-1989))

Figure (3): Antimicrobial Activity of PET/C Blended Fabric and Loaded with TiO₂ NPs, Determined by Shake Flask Method. (WC = Washing Cycle by AATCC Test Method (61-1989))

3.2.2. Ultraviolet Protection

Inorganic UV blockers are more preferable to organic UV blockers as they are non-toxic and chemically stable under exposure to both high temperatures and UV. Inorganic UV blockers are usually certain semiconductor oxides such as TiO₂, ZnO, SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ [23]. Among these semiconductor oxides, TiO₂ and ZnO are commonly used. Titanium dioxide and zinc oxide NPs were more efficient at absorbing and scattering UV radiation than the conventional size, and were thus better able to block UV [24]. This is due to the fact that NPs have a larger surface area per unit mass and volume than the conventional materials, leading to the increase of the effectiveness of blocking UV radiation. For small particles, light scattering predominates at approximately one-tenth of the wavelength of the scattered light [25].

Rayleigh's scattering theory stated that the scattering was strongly dependent upon the wavelength, where the scattering was inversely proportional to the wavelength to the fourth power. This theory predicts that in order to scatter UV radiation between 200 and 400 nm, the optimum particle size will be between 20 and 40 nm. The effect of activation of simultaneous treatment of PET and PET/C blended fabrics with sodium hydroxide and TiO₂ NPs, on UV protection efficiency was investigated. The rate of UV protection was quantified and expressed via UPF values that are given in Table (5). It was found that, the UPF factors for parents PET and PET/C blended fabrics are equal to 11.2 and 14.5 respectively. Activation with alkali treatment in presence TiO₂ NPs leads to deposition onto the above mentioned polyester fabrics surfaces NPs leading to a significant increase in UPF factor to the level corresponding to UPF rating of 40+ which assigns the excellent UV protection.

After five washing cycles the UPF values for PET and PET/C blended fabrics were decreased to 51 and 50+ respectively, which assigns excellent UV protection, respectively. These results show good laundering durability of PET fabrics and excellent laundering durability of PET and PET/C blended fabrics activated with alkali and loaded with TiO₂ NPs. The UPF values of the nano-TiO₂ treated PET and PET/C blended fabrics and dyed revealed that, dyeing causes decrease in the UPF values; but all samples still provide UPF.

Table (5): Ultraviolet Protection Factor (UPF) of Polyester Fabrics and Loaded with TiO₂ NPs

Fabrics	Number of Washing Cycles:			
	1*		5*	
	UPF	UPF Rating	UPF	UPF Rating
PET→B (Blank)	11.2	Poor	11.0	Poor
PET→B→H				
PET→B→H+ TiO ₂ 1 g/l	51.0	Excellent	33.5	Very good
PET→B→H+ TiO ₂ 1 g/l→D	32.9	Very good	28.7	Very good
PET/C→B (Blank)	14.5	Poor	14.2	Poor
PET/C→B→H				
PET/C→B→H+ TiO ₂ 1 g/l	50+	Excellent	50+	Excellent
PET/C→B→H+ TiO ₂ 1 g/l→D	46.5	Excellent	41.4	Excellent

3.2.3. Effect of Alkali Treatment and NPs on the Color Fastness

Comparing with traditional dyeing of polyester fabrics the color strengths obtained from dyeing of treated fabrics with NaOH in the presence of TiO₂ NPs leading to increase in wet-ability [26]. In higher concentrations of nano TiO₂, the oxygen vacancies (COOH and OH) are more accessible, resulting in higher capacity for water absorption. The higher wet-ability of the polyester fabrics treated improved the dye-ability [27]. Moreover, the

wet-ability was more prominent in fabrics dyed with disperse dye due to presence of more hydrophilic groups in the dye structure. Dye-ability has been related to crystallinity since decreasing crystallinity improves dye diffusion into the fiber and dye molecules penetrate much easier through amorphous regions, consequence results to effect of alkaline treatment conditions [28].

Therefore, a sufficient amorphous region was generated by alkaline treatment accompanied by enhancement in the dye-ability of treated polyester fabrics. In addition, NPs were chemically bonded on the fabric surfaces and acted as an adhesive agent between dye and fiber. Hence, large amount of dye molecules may react with the fabric [29]. Moreover, improved wet-ability of nano-treated fabrics can be directly assumed as an effective factor in higher dye adsorption [30]. The more nano TiO₂ on the fabric led to the higher dye uptake. Improving the color strength (K/S) of treated polyester fabrics dyed were also showed in Tables 6 and 7. This confirms the results obtained through absorbance spectra. Furthermore, superior changes in the hue, brightness, chroma, and color strength of all the samples, i.e. dyed and dyed pre-treated fabrics with sodium hydroxide in the presence of TiO₂ NPs [31].

Table (6): Effect of Alkali Treatment and loading TiO₂ NPs on the Color Fastness of PET fabrics

Sample dyed	k/s	Color Fastness to Wash			Color Fastness to crocking			Color Fastness to perspiration			Color Fastness to light		
		Change Value	Staining Value	Remark	Change Value	Staining Value	Remark	Change Value	Staining Value	Remark	Change Value	Staining Value	Remark
Blank	7.9	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	6	5	Good
0.2	8.3	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	6	5	Good
0.4	8.6	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	6	5	Good
0.6	8.8	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	4	5	Good
0.8	9	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	4	5	Good
1.0	9.6	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	4	5	Good

Table (7): Effect of Alkali Treatment and loading TiO₂ NPs on the Color Fastness of PET/C Fabrics

Sample dyed	k/s	Color Fastness to Wash			Color Fastness to crocking			Color Fastness to perspiration			Color Fastness to light		
		Change Value	Staining Value	Remark	Change Value	Staining Value	Remark	Change Value	Staining Value	Remark	Change Value	Staining Value	Remark
Blank	7.5	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	6	5	Good
0.2	7.9	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	6	5	Good
0.4	8.2	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	6	5	Good
0.6	8.5	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	4	5	Good
0.8	8.8	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	4	5	Good
1.0	8.9	5	4	Fast Good	5	4	Fast Good	4	3	Average	4	5	Good

4. Conclusion

This study describes a facile and benign approach for attaching TiO₂ NPs to the surfaces of PET and PET/C blended fabrics, as well as the effect of NPs on functional performance and dye-ability. This method involved simultaneously treating polyester fabrics with NaOH and TiO₂ NPs. The atomic % of Ti loaded on the dyed fabrics was determined using EDX analysis. The finished and dyed fabrics were characterized using SEM and FT-IR. Both color fastness and color strength (K/S) were evaluated. The results showed that even after five washing cycles, the TiO₂ NP loaded polyester fabrics had high antimicrobial and UV protection properties, indicating excellent laundering durability. The dye-ability and colorfastness measurements of PET and PET/C blended fabrics improved after dyeing. There is no doubt that, the results obtained in this research paving the way for the possibility of using metal oxides NPs on the production lines of dyeing and finishing factories. Also, in this research, a one-step dyeing technique was used for dyeing PET/C blended fabric in an alkaline medium,

which means the possibility of adding metal oxides NPs to the dyeing bath (dyeing and finishing in one step), which is the research that is currently being worked on.

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